

Design of Identification System and Counter of Motor Vehicles by Using Open CV Based Haar Cascade Method

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Abstract— Transportation is one of the factors that determine the success rate of development in an area that is consistent with the increase in human activity. Transport facilities and infrastructure can accommodate the needs of community movement, especially urban communities with high intensity of movement. Along with the increasing volume of vehicles today, transportation problems are still a major problem in a country especially developing countries. This transport problem has impacts on many sectors, from congestion to the resulting pollution problem. With the System of Identification and Counting of Motor Vehicles by Using Open-CV Haar Cascade Method, it is expected to know the number of vehicles passing through a certain point. By using CCTV video on the Jakarta road point and fly over PASUPATI eastward, the following results are obtained. for the morning Jakarta street session by 57% for cars and 34% for motorcycles, at 4% Jakarta street sessions for cars and 6% for motorcycles, on 119% nightlife sessions for cars and 111% for motorcycles, in the morning pasupati sessions 13% for cars and 16% for motorcycles, at 2% PASUPATI sessions for cars and 28% for motorcycles as well as on PASUPATI night gained 19% for cars and 28% for motorcycles. From the data it can be concluded that the average cauration of applications for automobiles is 36% and the accuracy of the motor is 34% and for the overall application is 35%. From these data can be concluded that the level of system accuracy is strongly influenced by the quality of the video used.

Keywords— transportation, traffic jam, CCTV, OpenCV, Haar Cascade

I. INTRODUCTION

Transportation is one of the factors that determine the success rate of development in an area that is consistent with the increase in human activity. Transport facilities and infrastructure can accommodate the needs of community movement, especially urban communities with high intensity of movement. Along with the increasing volume of vehicles today, transportation problems are still a major problem in a country especially developing countries. This transport problem has impacts on many sectors, from congestion to the resulting pollution problem. With the System of Identification and Counting of Motor Vehicles by Using Open-CV Haar Cascade Method, it is expected to know the number of vehicles passing through a certain point

A. OpenCV

Open CV (Open Source Computer Vision Library) is a library image processing created by intel and developed by Willow Garage. OpenCV is issued under license from BSD it makes it free for both academic and commercial use. OpenCV has C ++, C, Python and java interfaces and can be used on Windows, Linux, Mac OS, iOS and android operating systems. OpenCV is designed for computing efficiency and usage that focuses on real-time applications.

Written in optimized C / C ++ language, opencv library has advantages in multi-core processing. By enabling OpenCL, the library provides an advantage in hardware acceleration from a heterogeneous base count form.

B. Emgu CV

Emgu CV is a cross platform .Net wrapper for image processing libraries on openCV. Provides access to call functions in OpenCV through .Net programming languages such as C #, VB, VC ++, IronPython and so on. The wrapper can be operated (compiled) using Visual Studio, Xamarin Studio and Unity, the wrapper can be used on Windows, Linux, Mac OS X, iOS, Android and Windows Phone operating systems.

C. Haar Cascade

Haar Cascade is a machine learning object detection algorithm used to identify objects in an image or video. It is a machine learning based approach where a cascade function is trained from a lot of positive and negative images. It is then used to detect objects in other images.

The algorithm has four stages:

1. *Haar Feature Selection*
2. *Creating Integral Images*
3. *Adaboost Training*
4. *Cascading Classifiers*

II. SYSTEM DESIGN

The system is designed to recognize some object and to count it, where in this system the object are cars n motorcycle.

A. System Description

Vehicle counter is an OpenCV-based application that serves to calculate the number of vehicles in certain areas through CCTV. The vehicle counting area is marked with 4 (four) lines consisting of 2 (two) horizontal lines and 2 (two) vertical lines

combined to form a square. 2 (two) vertical lines serve as the boundary detection area so that the vehicle detection becomes more specific, while 2 (two) horizontal line serves as a prefix where the vehicle is calculated and the end from the calculated vehicle.

Fig. 1 system block diagram

B. System design

In designing vehicle counter application using C # programming language with Visual Studio 2015 as its development application. In the application use open CV as a library.

Fig.2 system flow chart

And the application appearance shown in fig. 3 below

Fig. 3 application appearance

In fig. 4 it shows how the application load with video opened in the application.

Fig. 4 application appearance with video opened

III. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULT

This application use video file from CCTV which placed in Jakarta road point and eastern PASUPATI fly over point. And the result are obtained. For the morning Jakarta street session by 57% for cars and 34% for motorcycles, at 4% Jakarta street sessions for cars and 6% for motorcycles, on 119% nightlife sessions for cars and 111% for motorcycles, in the morning pasupati sessions 13% for cars and 16% for motorcycles, at 2% PASUPATI sessions for cars and 28% for motorcycles as well as on PASUPATI night gained 19% for cars and 28% for motorcycles. From the data it can be concluded that the average cauration of applications for automobiles is 36% and the accuracy of the motor is 34% and for the overall application is 35%.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

From the data that shown in implementation section we can take a conclusion that the level of system accuracy is strongly influenced by the quality of the video used.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

For further research it will be nice if we use deep learning method, so we hope the accuracy of the system will be increased.

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